
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY INVESTMENT AND CORPORATE PRODUCTIVITY

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Abstract

This paper has conceptually examined the relationship between IT investment and corporate productivity. In-depth exploration of existing literatures was made to buttress the views expressed by the researcher and prior researchers as regard the subject matter evaluated.

The study employs the desk top review methodology by examining existing literature on the topic in order to get adequate first hand information.

Findings emanating from the conceptual evaluation indicate that IT investment is a major panacea and pre-requisite to firms that want to be frontiers in the industry, whether in financial or non- financial corporate organizations. Based on this, it is recommended that firms should always compare the marginal benefits of IT investment to the cost in terms of their general operations and attendant effect on productivity.

Keywords: IT investment, firm performance, productivity

Introduction

Due to globalization and the need to have a paradigm shift from the practices of dinosaur dynamics have actually brought to fore firms' tendency to embrace information technology (IT) investment so as to enhance performance and by extension productivity. IT investment takes the form of bringing computer hardware, electronic machines, terminals, cables just to name a few that assist companies do jobs faster than the human efforts. Firms in both financial and non-financial sector that over time have remained frontiers no doubt are IT investment friendly. One of the ways to differentiate productive corporate organizations from other is the level of investment they make in information technology (IT). IT investment decision is always meticulously done. Rajiu, Hsihui and Yi-Ching (2012) in this regard posit that to justify an IT investment, managers need to understand the potential benefits resulting from the investment. There is a general perception that IT investments by corporate organizations can improve productivity (Lee & Arentzoff, 2011). However, the impact of IT investment on firm productivity is not directly observable. In the view of Erik and Shinkyu (1996), several researchers have document that IT investment has positive effect on productivity. A careful review of existing literatures indicates that the relationship between IT investment and firm productive is inconclusive and mixed (Rajiu, Hsihui and Yi-Ching, 2012).

Moreover, interest in the "productivity paradox" as it has become known has engendered a significant amount of research; albeit analysis of prior researchers point out little evidence that information technology significantly increase productivity. While Berndt and Morrison (2005) report a negative correlation between productivity and IT investment, Jorgensan and Stiroh (2009) also report that IT investment has a significant positive effect on productivity. Against, this backdrop, this paper examines the relationship between IT investment and productivity. The remaining part of this paper is centered with literature review as well as conclusion and recommendations.

Literature Review

Concept of IT Investments

While an attempt is made to examine how IT investment influences firms' productivity, one may not afford to conclude blindly that IT investment on its own impact positively or otherwise without human influence which is capable of bringing out innovation in terms of products/services through the IT application. IT investment offers benefits for a wide range of business processes and improves the manner and ways activities are carried out in the course of the firms' day to day operations.

In the words of Koelingar (2006), the key to understanding the impacts of IT investment as it relates to productivity is to view IT as an enabler of innovation. Thus, the conceptualization of new technologies as possible enablers of innovation allows a market-based approach to study the relationship between IT investment and productivity (Koellingar, 2006). IT allows investigating why different firms that invest in the same technology tend to exhibit pay-offs. Moreover, the concept of IT investment permit anyone within this aspect of research to clearly argue that IT investment remains a strategic relevance for firms as long as it enables innovation, and innovation is a strategic variable because it allows firms to differentiate their products, services and production processes vis-à-vis their competitors, at least in the short-run.

Concept of Productivity

Simply put, productivity is efficiency in production: how much output is obtained from a given set of inputs. As such, it is typically expressed as an output–input ratio. Single-factor productivity measures reflect units of output produced per unit of a particular input. Labor productivity is the most common measure of this type, though occasionally capital or even materials productivity measures are used. Of course, single factor productivity levels are affected by the intensity of use of the excluded inputs.

Empirical relationship between IT Investment and productivity

Several researchers have demonstrated an increasingly significant relationship between IT investment and productivity (Oliner & Sichel 2000, Baily & Lawrence 2001). Gordon (2000) raised doubts about this productivity growth acceleration story and attributed most of the observed changes in US productivity to great IT investment. IT investment induces productivity and has varying significantly between sectors (Nordhaus, 2002). The largest productivity growth effect occurs in the IT producing sectors themselves, and only smaller (but still measurable) effects in sectors of an economy.

Because these complementary investments and organizational changes are highly firm specific, empirical studies show on average a positive return to IT investments, but with large variation across organizations (Pilat, 2005). Brynjolfsson and Hitt (2003) provided evidence that the returns to ICT investments usually do not occur immediately, but rather with a significant time lag. They find that computers make a positive and significant contribution to output growth at the firm level, but the implied returns increase if longer time differences are taken into account, which suggests that time-intensive complementary investments into organizational restructuring have to be undertaken. In a similar spirit, Hempell (2002) argues that firms with innovative experience are particularly well prepared to make productive use of IT by introducing appropriate complementary innovations. Bertschek and Kaiser (2004) show that IT investment has both direct indirect effects on productivity by enabling workplace re-organization and organizational change, stressing strong complementarities between these investments. Summarizing, IT is indeed a relevant part of current technological change processes and an important factor that contributes towards growth. However, the magnitude of impact on the firms' productivity varies significantly between firms, sectors and countries and can either be hampered or promoted by external factors. Also, there is growing consensus that the link between IT investment and productivity growth is rather indirect and that a positive impact arises only if IT investments are combined with complementary investments into innovation and human capital.

Organizations view investments in information technology (IT) as a way to combat competition by improving productivity, profitability, and quality of operations. The last decade has witnessed an unparalleled growth in investment in IT applications. The mainstream academic literature has documented numerous studies that examine the relationship between investments in technology and payoffs realized in terms of enhanced organizational performance (Brynjolfsson & Yang 1996; Kohli & Devaraj, 2003). It is evident that there are significant differences among studies in terms of the level of analyses, methodologies employed, variables, and contexts examined. Many economy-level studies Baily (1986); Roach (1987); Morrison and Berndt (1991) observed a negative relationship between technology-related variables and productivity. At the industry level the results are mixed, with some studies documenting a positive impact of technological investments (Kelley 1994, Siegel and Griliches, 1992) while other studies by Berndt and Morrison (1995) and Koski (1999) detect no significant advantage to IT investments. At the more-detailed firm level, Diewert and Smith (1994), Hitt and Brynjolfsson (1995), and Dewan and Min (1997)

present results indicating a positive relationship between technology and performance. Other firm-level studies by Menonet al. (2000) and Devaraj and Kohli (2000) found evidence of the positive effect of IT investment on productivity.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has theoretically and empirically evaluates how IT investments impacts on firms' productivity. While the concept of productivity is rather difficult to measure, it is the relationship between input and output. In this days of global challenges, organization that intend to be at the top most in the industry needs to embrace IT investments, train human capital to effectively and efficiently manage it with a view to enhancing the productivity and performance.

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